

Climate Change Drives Irrigation Expansion and Water Stress in the Serbian Danube

Sean Woznicki^{1,*}, Jamshid Jalali¹, Molly Sears², Noormah Rizwan², Tao Liu³, Judy Long⁴, Oskar Marko⁵, Mirjana Radulović⁵, Miljana Marković⁵, Nishan Bhattarai⁶

¹ Annis Water Resources Institute, Grand Valley State University, MI, USA, woznicse@gvsu.edu

² Department of Agricultural, Food, and Resource Economics, Michigan State University, MI, USA

³ Warnell School of Forestry and Natural Resources, University of Georgia, GA, USA

⁴ College of Forest Resources and Environmental Science, Michigan Technological University, MI, USA

⁵ BioSense Institute, Novi Sad, Vojvodina, Serbia

⁶ Department of Geography and Environmental Sustainability, University of Oklahoma, OK, USA

* corresponding author

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20408179

Abstract: In the Serbian Danube River Basin, growing season droughts are increasing in duration and severity. Reliance on rainfed agriculture is widespread, and expansion of irrigation is necessary to counteract warmer and drier conditions. Quantifying current and future agricultural water demand and availability is critical for effective water resources management. This research integrates remote sensing with coupled hydrological-economic modelling to map agricultural land use change, quantify changes in the water balance, and develop projections of mid-21st century irrigation expansion and water use. Annual cropland and irrigation maps were assimilated into the SWAT+ hydrological model and economic model. The economic model estimates how short- and long-run climate and water balance variables influence when and where irrigation becomes viable, and the hydrologic model estimates how water availability will change in response. Irrigation incentives increase in warmer and drier conditions and irrigation becomes viable for an additional 3-11% of fields by 2060 compared to 2020. Increasing crop water stress and declining soil moisture will require 10-20% increases in irrigation volumes to maintain the status quo. In total, irrigation expansion leads to additional water withdrawals of ~30 mm per year, which will exacerbate water balance deficits. The modest increase in irrigation expansion thus reflects that infrastructure constraints limit adaptation even though climate-driven incentives increase.

Keywords: drought; irrigation; agriculture; hydrological modelling; economic modelling.

1 Introduction

Rising atmospheric and ocean temperatures have altered precipitation and evapotranspiration (ET), resulting in soil moisture depletion observed over the previous two decades (Seo et al. 2025). NASA GRACE/GRACE-FO data revealed that continents have undergone terrestrial water storage loss since 2002, attributable in part to global groundwater depletion for irrigation and intense European droughts (Chandanpurkar et al. 2025). By 2050, 60% of global croplands are projected to have less water (primarily via reduced soil moisture), and nearly 25% of croplands will have greater crop water requirements (Liu et al. 2022).

These trends are evident in central and Eastern Europe, where summer droughts are becoming more frequent

(Spinoni et al. 2018). Serbia, for example, had nine regional or country-wide severe droughts since 2000 (Djordjević et al. 2024), with the 2017 drought resulting in 30-60% yield reductions in summer crops (Mimić et al. 2022). Despite these vulnerabilities, only 8% of cropland in Serbia is irrigated (SORS, 2024), the country is prioritizing expansion of irrigation (Bezdan et al. 2019), rehabilitating irrigation infrastructure (Županić et al. 2021), and constructing multi-user irrigation systems (Goss 2021).

Recurring droughts, increasing soil moisture deficits, climate change, and the potential for irrigation expansion in Serbia create a pressing need to quantify future water availability and potential alternatives of increased water use due to irrigation expansion. We developed an approach that combined remote sensing with coupled hydrological-economic modelling to understand cropland and irrigation dynamics in the region, how and where irrigation expansion might occur in response to climate-driven water scarcity, and how water availability will change in response. This paper summarizes coordinated efforts (Jalali et al. 2025, Long et al. 2026, Rizwan et al. 2025) toward this goal.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The Serbian Danube River Basin (SDRB) encompasses 98% of Serbia. Climate zones are predominantly Cfa (temperate climate, fully humid with hot summers) in the north and Cfb (temperate climate, fully humid with warm summers) in the south (Mimić et al. 2024). Annual precipitation ranges from 517 mm in the northern Vojvodina province to 993 mm in the mountainous southwest. The largest share of agriculture is in the drier parts of the country, particularly the Vojvodina province, which has around 1.43 million ha of cereals, fodder crops, and vegetables (58% of Serbia's arable land) (SORS 2024).

2.2 Hydrological modelling

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool Plus (SWAT+) model (Bieger et al. 2017) for the SDRB was developed to simulate the water balance in current and future conditions. The SWAT+ simulates rainfall-runoff processes, ET, soil moisture, irrigation, river routing, groundwater recharge, crop growth, and nutrient cycling. Key inputs include a digital elevation model, soil maps, land use maps, and

gridded daily weather data. The model was discretized using a 2 km grid, with each grid cell composed of multiple hydrological response units (HRUs). HRUs are unique combinations of soil type, land use, and slope. Full details of the model implementation for this research are presented in Jalali et al. (2025). Brief descriptions of key model characteristics are presented below.

Crop rotations and irrigation were implemented at the HRU level. Sentinel-2 based annual crop maps from 2016-2022 (Živaljević et al. 2024) were used to develop seven-year crop trajectories for Vojvodina province, of which greater than 36,000 were ingested into the model. The irrigation maps, also derived from Sentinel-2 (Radulović et al. 2023), were implemented in a similar manner for maize, soybeans, and sugar beets - the most commonly irrigated crops in the region. Irrigation sources were determined based on proximity to surface water source (< 5 km to water body = surface water, else, groundwater) and irrigation initiation was triggered via a crop water stress threshold (CWS) ($1 - ET/PET$) of greater than 0.2, with irrigation occurring until the soil reached field capacity.

Model calibration and uncertainty analysis were performed using (1) monthly discharge measurements at two river gages from 1988-2008, (2) remotely sensed Penman-Monteith-Leuning ET at 500 m resolution (Zhang et al. 2019), aggregated to monthly totals from 2002-2020. The calibration and uncertainty routine was conducted using the SWAT Parameter Estimator algorithm (Abbaspour et al. 2015) with an objective function maximizing the Nash Sutcliffe Coefficient of Efficiency. This produced 95% prediction uncertainty bands for each model output. Full calibration and uncertainty metrics are reported in Jalali et al. (2025).

2.3 Climate model scenarios

The CMIP5 EURO-CORDEX regional climate models (RCMs), bias-corrected by Dosio (2016), were ingested into the SWAT+ to simulate the water balance and crop growth in 2041-2070. Five GCM-RCMs across RCP 4.5 and 8.5 were selected: CCLM-CNRM-C5, CCLM-EC-EARTH, CCLM-MPI-ESM-LR, WRF-IPSL-CM5A, and RACMO-EC-EARTH. The wettest (WRF-IPSL-CM5A) and driest (CCLM-MPI-ESM-LR) models from RCP 4.5 (hereafter, “wet/dry scenario” and “wet/dry model”) based on annual average precipitation were used in the economic modelling of irrigation adoption. Annual mean temperatures from 2041-2070 are projected to increase by 0.75-1.6 °C from a 1991-2020 baseline across all models and RCPs. Projected precipitation changes are more uncertain - model ensemble (mean) estimates suggest the non-growing seasons become wetter and the growing seasons become drier.

2.4 Economic modelling of irrigation adoption

The economic modelling approach is framed using the following question: if an agricultural producer in 2020 was confronted with climatic conditions projected in future years, how would their decision to irrigate change (Rizwan et al. 2025)? The agricultural producer’s decision to adopt irrigation was represented as a function of expected

profitability, which is influenced by previous season and long-term weather conditions, field conditions, irrigation costs, and farm characteristics. The irrigation adoption model was developed using irrigation maps (Radulović et al. 2023) and crop maps (Živaljević et al. 2024) for the Vojvodina province, soil moisture data from SWAT+, surface and groundwater irrigation costs (proxied by distance from surface water and aquifer productivity), soil available water capacity, and field size. The probability of irrigation adoption was estimated using a logit model. The full model specification is presented in Rizwan et al. (2025). The model was then coupled offline with SWAT+ to simulate the expansion of irrigation in 2041-2070 and its effect on the water balance. The full workflow is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Simplified workflow connecting the hydrological and economic models to project future irrigation extent and volume in 2041-2070.

3 Results

3.1 Water balance in 2041-2070

The water balance and crop water stress are projected to change, shifting toward drier conditions driven by temperature and PET (evaporative demand) increases coupled with a reduction in summer precipitation and soil

Figure 2. (A) crop water stress for Jan-Feb-Mar (JFM), Apr-May-Jun (AMJ), Jul-Aug-Sep (JAS), and Oct-Nov-Dec (OND), (B) ensemble mean change in CWS during JAS under RCP4.5 and (C) RCP8.5. Adapted from Jalali et al. (2025).

moisture. The CWS in July-August-September, a time of significant water needs for summer crops, increases significantly, these changes are greatest in southern Serbia, which has lower agricultural productivity (Figure 2). Although CWS decreases are not as strong in northern Serbia, this region is the driest in the country, so any change in CWS could have a large impact.

Mean annual irrigation water use amounts to 180 mm yr⁻¹ (about 0.082 km³ yr⁻¹) which is within the range of estimates for the country in global studies (Puy et al. 2021). Irrigation is projected to increase to 196-237 mm yr⁻¹ in RCP4.5 or 179-217 mm yr⁻¹ in RCP8.5. We analysed irrigated versus rainfed agricultural fields with similar crop rotations (maize, soybeans, sugar beets), comparing how the combined effects of irrigation and climate change impact the field-scale water balance (Figure 3). The irrigation replenishes soil water and contributes to ET. Ultimately, irrigation reduces crop water stress, but demand will increase in the future, as evidenced by greater irrigation depths. Note that this comparison does not account for potential for irrigation expansion, which is reported in Section 3.2.

Figure 3. Comparison of irrigated versus rainfed grid cells for July-August-September water balance variables. Adapted from Jalali et al. (2025).

3.2 Irrigation expansion

Results of the logistic regression model found that irrigation decisions can be linked to soil moisture and field size. A one mm increase in soil moisture during the previous growing season decreases the likelihood of irrigation adoption by 0.011 percentage points (statistically significant at 1% level). Conversely, a one mm increase in 30-year average historical soil moisture increases the likelihood of adoption by 0.023 percentage points (statistically significant at 1% level). Field size is also significant, with larger fields likely able to absorb capital costs associated with irrigation equipment. Full model results are presented in Rizwan et al. (2025).

Coupling the regression model with the SWAT+ climate change model runs (RCP4.5 dry scenario and wet scenario), we project 143,351 additional fields to adopt irrigation under the dry scenario and 39,490 fields to adopt irrigation under the wet scenario, from a baseline of 15,416 fields. This results in significant irrigation expansion (up to an additional 30 mm yr⁻¹) in the dry scenario and increases

water balance deficits in dry years (Figure 4). The effect is less pronounced in the wet scenario, as greater precipitation volumes offset soil moisture deficits.

Figure 4. (A and B) annual water balance ($WB = P-ET$) anomalies for dry and wet scenarios, respectively, (C and D) irrigation volume anomalies. Adapted from (Rizwan et al. 2025).

4 Discussion

The warmer and drier conditions in the growing season in Serbia, coupled with increased evaporative demand, are projected to drive soil moisture decline and crop water stress in Serbia. Given that the country largely relies on rainfed agriculture, adaptation will be required – potentially in the form of irrigation investment to maintain yields. This process is already underway in parts of the country through various mechanisms (Bezdan et al. 2019, Goss 2021, Županić et al. 2021). The coupled hydrological-economic modelling approach found that short- and long-run declining soil moisture prompts farmers to adopt irrigation, which becomes extensive under warmer and drier conditions. This is in line with previous studies that use precipitation as a proxy for soil moisture, although our approach accounts for ET losses and humidity (Proctor et al. 2022). We find a 256% (wet scenario) to 830% (dry scenario) increase in irrigating fields in the Vojvodina province, which results in a modest increase in water use but will compound the more significant effects of climate change on water availability.

Agricultural adaptation needs will vary spatially because the impacts of climate change are not equally distributed – southern Serbia (which is wetter compared to the north) will face greater increases in CWS (Figure 2). Producers with orchards and annual fruits and vegetables, more commonly irrigated (Goss, 2021), will readily adapt. Southern Serbia has experienced population loss and agricultural land abandonment (Živanović et al. 2022), and increasing water scarcity may exacerbate abandonment. Conversely, in the drier north and central Serbia, projected warmer and wetter springs may support expansion of winter wheat. Limited water stress in the early growing season due to wetter winters may also allow for earlier planting of summer crops. If irrigation expansion is out of

reach, other alternatives may include switching to less water intensive crops or varieties or taking marginal land out of production, although they too have a cost.

5 Conclusions

Hotter and drier conditions in Serbia will increase evaporative demand and decrease soil moisture, which increases crop water stress and subsequent demand for irrigation. Projections of mid-21st century irrigation expansion show producers' responsiveness to soil moisture conditions, resulting in 8-fold increases in irrigated fields and up to 30 mm of additional irrigation. As Serbia's agriculture is primarily rainfed, these estimates are in line with ongoing efforts to increase irrigation in the country, which will likely add stress to water resources. These studies (Jalali et al. 2025, Rizwan et al. 2025) demonstrated that a remote sensing-hydrological-economic modeling approach can develop high-resolution projections of the water balance, water use, and potential irrigation expansion.

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by NASA Land Cover and Land Use Change grant #80NSSC22K0467.

6 References

- Abbaspour, K.C., Rouholahnejad, E., Vaghefi, S., Srinivasan, R., Yang, H., Kløve, B., 2015. A continental-scale hydrology and water quality model for Europe: Calibration and uncertainty of a high-resolution large-scale SWAT model. *Journal of Hydrology* 524, 733–752.
- Bezdan, A., Blagojevic, B., Vranesevic, M., Benka, P., Savic, R., Bezdan, J., 2019. Defining Spatial Priorities for Irrigation Development Using the Soil Conservation and Water Use Efficiency Criteria. *Agronomy* 9, 324.
- Bieger, K., Arnold, J.G., Rathjens, H., White, M.J., Bosch, D.D., Allen, P.M., Volk, M., Srinivasan, R., 2017. Introduction to SWAT+, A Completely Restructured Version of the Soil and Water Assessment Tool. *JAWRA Journal of the American Water Resources Association* 53, 115–130.
- Chandanpurkar, H.A., Famiglietti, J.S., Gopalan, K., Wiese, D.N., Wada, Y., Kakinuma, K., Reager, J.T., Zhang, F., 2025. Unprecedented continental drying, shrinking freshwater availability, and increasing land contributions to sea level rise. *Science Advances* 11, eadx0298.
- Djurdjević, V., Stosic, B., Tošić, M., Lazić, I., Putniković, S., Stosic, T., Tošić, I., 2024. Analysis of recent trends and spatiotemporal changes of droughts over Serbia using high-resolution gridded data. *Atmospheric Research* 304, 107376.
- Dosio, A., 2016. Projections of climate change indices of temperature and precipitation from an ensemble of bias-adjusted high-resolution EURO-CORDEX regional climate models. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 121, 5488–5511.
- Goss, S., 2021. Brief 6: Irrigation in Serbia, Supporting the development of an irrigation strategy for Serbia. FAO.
- Jalali, J., Bhattarai, N., Greene, J., Liu, T., Marko, O., Radulović, M., Sears, M., Woznicki, S.A., 2025. Climate change threatens water resources for major field crops in the Serbian Danube River Basin by the mid-21st century. *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies* 59, 102404.
- Liu, X., Liu, W., Tang, Q., Liu, B., Wada, Y., Yang, H., 2022. Global Agricultural Water Scarcity Assessment Incorporating Blue and Green Water Availability Under Future Climate Change. *Earth's Future* 10, e2021EF002567.
- Long, J., Liu, T., Woznicki, S.A., Marković, M., Marko, O., Sears, M., 2026. From time-series generation and model selection to transfer learning: A review and comparative analysis of pixel-wise approaches for large-scale crop mapping. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 246, 111646.
- Mimić, G., Podračanin, Z., Basarin, B., 2024. Change detection of the Köppen climate zones in Southeastern Europe. *Atmospheric Science Letters* 25, e1270.
- Mimić, G., Živaljević, B., Blagojević, D., Pejak, B., Brdar, S., 2022. Quantifying the Effects of Drought Using the Crop Moisture Stress as an Indicator of Maize and Sunflower Yield Reduction in Serbia. *Atmosphere* 13, 1880.
- Proctor, J., Rigden, A., Chan, D., Huybers, P., 2022. More accurate specification of water supply shows its importance for global crop production. *Nat Food* 3, 753–763.
- Puy, A., Borgonovo, E., Lo Piano, S., Levin, S.A., Saltelli, A., 2021. Irrigated areas drive irrigation water withdrawals. *Nat Commun* 12, 4525.
- Radulović, M., Brdar, S., Pejak, B., Lugonja, P., Athanasiadis, I., Pajević, N., Pavić, D., Crnojević, V., 2023. Machine learning-based detection of irrigation in Vojvodina (Serbia) using Sentinel-2 data. *GIScience & Remote Sensing* 60, 2262010.
- Rizwan, N., Jalali, J., Sears, M., Woznicki, S.A., Liu, T., Marko, O., Radulović, M., 2025. Irrigation adoption in a changing landscape: a combined economic and hydrologic approach.
- Seo, K.-W., Ryu, D., Jeon, T., Youm, K., Kim, J.-S., Oh, E.H., Chen, J., Famiglietti, J.S., Wilson, C.R., 2025. Abrupt sea level rise and Earth's gradual pole shift reveal permanent hydrological regime changes in the 21st century. *Science*.
- SORS, 2024. Census of Agriculture 2023. Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, Republic of Serbia.
- Spinoni, J., Vogt, J.V., Naumann, G., Barbosa, P., Dosio, A., 2018. Will drought events become more frequent and severe in Europe? *International Journal of Climatology* 38, 1718–1736.
- Zhang, Y., Kong, D., Gan, R., Chiew, F.H.S., McVicar, T.R., Zhang, Q., Yang, Y., 2019. Coupled estimation of 500 m and 8-day resolution global evapotranspiration and gross primary production in 2002–2017. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 222, 165–182.
- Živaljević, B., Marković, M., Mimić, G., Marko, O., Woznicki, S., 2024. Multi-annual crop maps reveal cropping patterns in the Vojvodina region (Serbia), in: 2024 12th International Conference on Agro-Geoinformatics, pp. 1–4.
- Živanović, V., Joksimović, M., Golić, R., Malinić, V., Krstić, F., Sedlak, M., Kovjanić, A., 2022. Depopulated and Abandoned Areas in Serbia in the 21st Century—From a Local to a National Problem. *Sustainability* 14, 10765.
- Županić, F.Ž., Radić, D., Podbregar, I., 2021. Climate change and agriculture management: Western Balkan region analysis. *Energy Sustain Soc* 11, 1–9.